

Laponite-Based Nano-emulsions of Amazonian Essential Oils

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Abstract

This study investigated the behaviour of essential oil-in-water emulsions (O/W) containing *Bursera graveolens*, and *Ocotea quixos* essential oils. To enhance their topical administration and stability, Laponite (a synthetic, hectorite-like clay) was added at different concentrations to the continuous phase. All formulations were assessed in terms of time-stability, particle size, zeta potential, antioxidant activity, rheological properties, and *in vitro* cytotoxicity. Despite the excellent encapsulation capacity of essential oils, the addition of 3% w/w Laponite accelerated emulsion instability at extreme conditions. In contrast, this inorganic ingredient significantly improved the rheological properties for topical administration. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) was used to characterize the morphology of the emulsions, showing a layer of Laponite particles around the essential oil droplets, a typical feature of Pickering emulsions. Cytotoxicity studies confirmed that O/W emulsions were not toxic for cells, a result strengthened by 3% w/w of Laponite. In conclusion, O/W microemulsion from *Bursera graveolens* and *Ocotea*

36 *quixos* essential oils proved stable and safe as topical formulations. Rheological
37 performance and in vitro cytotoxicity can be modulated by the addition of Laponite,
38 although its concentration must be optimized.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 The Amazon Rainforest is the largest humid tropical forest on the planet, considered the
41 region with the highest biodiversity of fauna and flora, estimated to be home to 10% of the
42 Earth's known species [1,2]. Among the minority of plant species used for medicinal or
43 therapeutic purposes *Bursera graveolens* and *Ocotea quixos* can be mentioned. Among the
44 main properties of these species, the content of essential oils (EO) can be highlighted.

45

46 Essential oils (EOs) are concentrated, volatile and odorous compounds extracted from
47 aromatic and/or medicinal plants [3]. These volatile compounds are innate constituents of
48 plants to which they provide different effects, from defence against pathogens, herbivores
49 to insect attraction (to disperse pollen and seed) or repellent [4]. EOs contain a complex
50 mixture of chemical constituents (terpenes, aldehydes, esters, and phenols) which
51 contribute to their distinctive scent and therapeutic effects. Due to their high volatility,
52 rapid degradation and lipophilicity, EOs are compounds difficult to use efficiently in
53 pharmaceutical, and cosmetic products [3]. Moreover, the direct use of EO is not advisable
54 due to their irritant nature.

55

56 *Bursera graveolens* (*Burseraceae*) is a specie of the commonly known as Torchwood family,
57 incense and myrrh family, due to the complex mixtures of volatile compounds awarding
58 them with characteristic aromas and medicinal properties [5]. *Bursera graveolens*, also
59 known as "Palo Santo" or "holy branch" [6] receives its common name due to the spicy,
60 sweet and balsamic odour of dried wood, which is dried and burned in churches. This wood,
61 as well as its essential oil are used as insecticide and repellent [5–9]. Together with burned
62 wood, Palo Santo EO possesses analgesic, anti-inflammatory, sedative and diaphoretic
63 activities [5–7,10]. Likewise, antioxidant, antimicrobial and antifungal activities are
64 important biological activities found in Palo santo EO [7,11,12].

65

66 Ishpingo is the common name for *Ocotea quixos* (*Laureaceae*) plant. This name is related
67 to its strong smell of cinnamon [13]. From the Incas age, this plant and its essential oil have
68 been used for its aromatic properties, and as anaesthetic or analgesic [13,14], probably

69 related to its anti-inflammatory activities. Antibacterial, antifungal, larvicide,
70 antispasmodic, antidiabetic, antithrombotic, muscle relaxant and repellent can also be
71 mentioned [14–18]. As general in plant essential oils, *Ocotea quixos* possesses remarkable
72 antioxidant activity [14–16,18,19].

73

74 Emulsions (especially micro- and nano-emulsions) have proven to be useful allies in the
75 formulation of EO, thanks to their ability to effectively encapsulate them in small droplets,
76 making them more stable and expanding their applications [3]. Micro- and nanoemulsions
77 are clear, thermodynamically stable systems composed of oil, water, and surfactant, often
78 accompanied by a co-surfactant, which allows for the seamless integration of essential
79 oils. Differences between micro- and nano-emulsions are related to their droplet size,
80 thermodynamic stability, final viscosity, preparation method and surfactant concentration
81 [20–23]. Droplet size range is a not well-defined criterion, since different ranges can be
82 found in the literature. In general, bigger and wider droplet sizes are defined for
83 nanoemulsions (20-200 nm or 20-600 nm) [23,24], while microemulsions are often
84 between 1-100 nm, 10-100 nm or 100-400 nm [20,24]. According to Kale and Deore [20]
85 microemulsions have “low viscosity”, while nanoemulsions are associated with viscosities
86 around 1 cP at room temperature (very low viscosities). Low surfactant concentration (3-
87 10% w/w) and high energy emulsification methods are also related to nanoemulsion rather
88 than microemulsions [20]. These kind of formulations not only improve the bioavailability
89 of the oils but also enhances their stability and controlled release, ensuring more effective
90 delivery of their therapeutic properties. By harnessing the benefits of micro and nano-
91 emulsion technology, EO can be used more effectively in a range of skincare and health
92 applications, providing both functional and sensory benefits. Nevertheless, both micro-
93 and nano-emulsions are generally liquids with low or very low viscosities [20], complicating
94 their topical administration.

95

96 Clay minerals are one of the most employed solid particles in rheology modification. In
97 some cases, the addition of clay particles to the external phase creates the so-called
98 nanoemulgels. The clay particles have demonstrated to concentrate in the oil-water
99 interface, together with surfactants, as well as in the continuous aqueous phase.
100 Additionally, clay particles can locate in the EO-water interphase, subsequently influencing
101 the stability and rheology of the final emulsion [25–29]. Although the successful use of clay
102 particles as emulsion stabilizers has widely been reported [25,30–33], it is necessary to

103 optimize their performance: as previously stated in the literature, the mere use of clay
 104 particles as emulsion stabilizers is not enough for the long term [34].
 105 Laponite® (Lap) is particularly promising as emulsion ingredient since it can be easily
 106 exfoliated in water as a colloidal suspension [32], providing effective viscosity increase and
 107 thixotropic behaviour [35]. Its synthetic nature is also convenient due to its higher purity,
 108 safety and quality control. This clay has been mainly used for polymer particles[32,36,37],
 109 while its use in EO oil-in-water emulsions has not been commonly reported in the literature.

110

111 The aim of this study is to prepare, develop and characterise nanoemulsions prepared with
 112 two essential oils extracted from Amazon rainforest plants. Essential oils (EO) were
 113 analytically characterized and the physicochemical stability of nanoemulsions were
 114 evaluated at different conditions. Due to the low viscosity of these formulations, synthetic
 115 clay mineral (Laponite) was used as inorganic excipient to improve consistency and,
 116 potentially, favour emulsion stability: the inorganic gel formed by Lap particles dispersions
 117 can entrap EO droplets and prevent their coalescence. Therefore, the impact of this mineral
 118 in the formulations was studied. Finally, the *in vitro* cytotoxicity and antioxidant activity of
 119 all the formulations (with and without Laponite) were also assessed.

120

121 2. Materials and Methods

122 2.1. Materials

123 EO extracted from *Bursera graveolens* (PS) and *Ocotea quixos* (OQ) were kindly donated by
 124 University of Loja (Ecuador). Details about the extraction method are gathered in **Table 1**.
 125 They were used as oil phase of each microemulsion, also composed by Polysorbate 80
 126 (HLB 15) as non-ionic surfactant (Guinama, Valencia, Spain). Laponite® XLG (Lap) acted as
 127 rheological agent and was kindly donated by BYK (Wesel, Germany). All formulations were
 128 prepared using ultrapure water (18.2 MΩ·cm), obtained by means of a Milli-Q system
 129 (Millipore®, Burlington, MA, USA).

130

131 *Table 1. Extraction method used for each EO, including plant part used and reference.*

Essential Oil	Plant part	Extraction method	Ref
PS	Fresh fruits	Hydro-distillation (Clevenger-type apparatus for 180 min)	[38]
OQ	Fresh leaves	Hydro-distillation (Clevenger-type apparatus for 340 min)	[13]

132

133 For the analytical characterisation of EO analytical-grade standards of limonene [1-methyl-
134 4-(prop-1-en-2-yl)cyclohex-1-ene], sabinene [4-methylene-1-(1-
135 methylethyl)bicyclo[3.1.0]hexane], β -phellandrene [3-methylidene-6-(propan-2-
136 yl)cyclohex-1-ene], β -elemene [(1S,2S,4R)-1-methyl-2,4-di(prop-1-en-2-yl)-1-
137 vinylcyclohexane], β -ocimene [3,7-dimethylocta-1,3,6-triene], β -pinene [(1S,5S)-6,6-
138 dimethyl-2-methylidenebicyclo[3.1.1]heptane], α -pinene (1S,5S)-2,6,6-
139 trimethylbicyclo[3.1.1]hept-2-ene], β -caryophyllene [(1R,4E,9S)-4,11,11-trimethyl-8-
140 methylidenebicyclo[7.2.0]undec-4-ene], p-cymene (1-methyl-4-propan-2-ylbenzene) and
141 xylene (dimethylbenzene), used as the internal standard (IS), as well as analytical-grade
142 acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH) and ammonium acetate, were obtained from Merck
143 Life Science (Darmstadt, Germany). Analyte and IS stock solutions (1 mg/mL) were
144 prepared in MeOH and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while working solutions were prepared daily by
145 dilution in mobile phase and stored protected from light in amber glass vials (when
146 required).

147

148 For antioxidant activity 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH \bullet), 2,4,6-Tris(2-pyridyl)-
149 s-triazine (TPTZ) and FeCl_3 reagents were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) and
150 used as received. All other substances are analytical grade and for the biological
151 experiment the materials are described in the specific methodology.

152 **2.2. Methods**

153 **2.2.1. Preparation of Nanoemulsion**

154 All emulsions (O/W) were prepared in two stages. Firstly, direct emulsification was
155 performed. Ultra-purified water was mixed with $\leq 3\%$ w/w of Polysorbate 80 (HLB 15, **Table**
156 **2**) and subjected to magnetic stirring for 5-10 minutes. Then, the oil phase, composed of
157 100% of each EO, was added to the aqueous phase dropwise while subjected to high-speed
158 agitation via UltraTurrax T-25 (IKA $^{\circ}$ Werke GmbH & Co. KG Janke & Kunkel, Staufen,
159 Germany) working at 20,000 rpm for 10 minutes. As a second stage, ultrasonic processor
160 (Sonifier 450, Branson Ultrasonics Corporation, Danbury, Connecticut, U.S.A.) was used
161 for 15 minutes (constant mode), to further reduce the EO droplet dimension (O/W). At this
162 step the temperature of the nanoemulsion was controlled with an ice water bath, thus
163 preventing an excessive increase in temperature during ultrasonication. Due to the high-
164 energy emulsification method and the concentration of surfactant used, “nanoemulsions”
165 were obtained.

166

167 Lap was added to some of the nanoemulsions to evaluate its impact over the formulation.
 168 To do so, Lap (2% or 3% w/w) was added over the pristine emulsion, followed by magnetic
 169 stirring for 24 hours to guarantee effective dispersion of clay nanoparticles in the aqueous
 170 phase [39–41]. The final composition of each group of emulsions are summarized in **Table**
 171 **2**.

173 *Table 2. Final composition of O/W nanoemulsions with and without Lap. Since Lap was added over the pristine*
 174 *formulation, the total % w/w composition varies. All EO were used at the same concentration.*

Formulation	Purified water (% w/w)	Polysorbate 80 (% w/w)	EO* (% w/w)	Lap (% w/w)
Without Lap	93	3	4	-
With Lap	91.17	2.94	3.92	2
	90.29	2.91	3.88	3

175 *Code use for each EO: PS = *B. graveolens*; OQ = *O. quixos*.

176
 177 Emulsions without Lap were codified as E+”essential oil code” (EPS or EOQ). For emulsions
 178 containing 2% or 3% w/w Lap, the codes “_2L” or “_3L” were included, respectively
 179 (EPS_2L, EOQ_2L and EPS_3L, EOQ_3L).

180 **2.2.2. Analytical Characterization of Essential Oils**

181 Capillary electrochromatography coupled to diode array detection (CEC-DAD) analyses
 182 were carried out on a 3DCE capillary electrophoresis apparatus from Agilent Technologies
 183 (Santa Clara, CA, USA), equipped with a DAD operating at 210 nm, following Micucci and
 184 co-workers procedure [42]. Fused silica capillary (32 cm total length x 100 µm ID, 375 OD)
 185 was from Polymicro Technologies (Phoenix, AZ, US) and packed with LiChrospher 100 RP-
 186 18 endcapped particles (5 µm particle size, 100 Å pore size) from Merck-Millipore. The
 187 optimised mobile phase consisted of 50 mM ammonium acetate solution (pH 5) mixed with
 188 ACN (17/83, V/V), which was kept at constant temperature of 25 °C. Analyses were carried
 189 out applying a 35 kV voltage and 8 bar pressure at both ends of the capillary, and samples
 190 (EO) were injected at the anodic end of the capillary by applying a pressure of 5 bar for 30 s.

191
 192 Before EO analysis, the method was fully validated on analyte standard solutions,
 193 according to the main international guidelines in terms of precision, linearity (including
 194 Limit of Detection (LOD), and limit of quantitation (LOQ)) and accuracy (ICH Harmonised
 195 Guideline M10)[43].

196

197 Regarding sample analysis, 3-mg sample aliquots were extracted by adding 1 mL MeOH
198 and subjected to vortex agitation for 30 s and ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) for 15
199 min. The suspension was then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min, the supernatant was
200 filtered through 0.2 µm pore diameter nylon syringe filters, transferred in autosampler vials,
201 suitably diluted in mobile phase whenever necessary, and analysed by CEC-DAD. Analyte
202 quantitation was obtained by integrating peak areas obtained from sample analysis and
203 interpolation on the linearity curve of each analyte. All analyses were carried out in
204 triplicate by CEC-DAD on a single batch of samples. Quantitative results were then
205 expressed as ng/mL[42].

206

207 **2.2.3. Antioxidant Activity of Essential Oils (DPPH method)**

208 The DPPH method uses 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical to evaluate the
209 antioxidant properties of natural products, as the violet free radical is transformed from
210 reductants to yellow hydrazine through a formal hydrogen atom transfer reaction[44]. The
211 interaction of tested EOs with DPPH radicals led to the rapid discoloration of the DPPH
212 solution. This DPPH method determines the antioxidant activity in terms of free radical
213 scavenging activity. The activity of radical scavenging was determined by preparing an EOs
214 stock solution (5 mg/mL in MeOH). Concentration series of each EO were prepared by
215 diluting the corresponding stock solution (from 0 to 4.5 mg/mL). 1 mL of DPPH solution (1.5
216 $\times 10^{-4}$ M in MeOH) was then vigorously mixed with 1.0 mL of sample and incubated at room
217 temperature in the dark for 40 min. The percentage of inhibition of DPPH free radicals (I%)
218 was calculated from **Eq. 1**, where A_0 is the absorbance of the DPPH solution without
219 essential oil ($\lambda_{\max} = 513$ nm) and A_{EO} is the absorbance of the tested EO sample. All tests
220 were carried out in duplicate, results expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

221

$$I\% = \frac{A_0 - A_{EO}}{A_0} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

222

223 **2.2.4. Nanoemulsions characterization**

224 **2.2.4.1. Qualitative, Macroscopic Analysis: Physical Behaviour**

225 Approximately 1.5 g of each nanoemulsion was qualitatively evaluated for changes in
226 consistency, homogeneity and colour by visual observation. The macroscopic analysis of
227 the organoleptic characteristics was determined at room temperature (25 °C) with natural

228 light. All the analyses were carried out by comparing them with the 36 hours of emulsion
229 preparation.

230 Samples were evaluated and compared at 1, 7, 14 and 28 days after their preparation.

231

232 Since emulsions are especially sensitive to thermal stress, aliquots of each sample were
233 stored at different temperatures (40 °C, inside an oven; 8 °C inside a refrigerator) for 28
234 days. Storage at various temperatures can accelerate but not alter the mechanism of
235 deterioration with respect to normal storage conditions, thus making possible to detect
236 ulterior alterations at shorter times. These tests were performed immediately after sample
237 preparation. Macroscopic analysis of these samples was likewise performed after 1, 7, 14
238 and 28 days.

239

240 **2.2.4.2. Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS): particle size, polydispersity index and zeta** 241 **potential studies**

242 A ZetaSizer Nano ZS equipment (Malvern® Instruments, Malvern, UK) was used to
243 determine the hydrodynamic size, polydispersity index (PDI) and zeta potential (ZP) of each
244 sample (with and without Lap). To do so, samples were diluted (1:100) in ultra-purified
245 water (MilliQ-grade, Millipore®) and analysed under a scattering angle of 173°. All
246 parameters were determined in triplicate (for each sample) at 7 and 25 days after their
247 preparation and operating at 25 °C. Results are reported as mean ± standard deviation.

248

249 **2.2.4.3. pH assessment**

250 The pH of viscous nanoemulsions (those containing 3% w/w Lap) was monitored with a pH
251 meter PH 25+ (Crison, Shilu Instruments, Shanghai, China), while liquid samples were
252 studied with a pH meter BASIC 20+ (Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain) at room
253 temperature (25 °C). The measurements were taken in triplicate, after 1, 7, 14, and 28 days.
254 Since the prepared formulations are intended for dermal administration, their pH must be
255 carefully addressed. Moreover, pH changes are related to some
256 destabilization/degradation mechanism, especially when it comes to natural oils.

257

258 **2.2.4.4. Antioxidant Activity of Nanoemulsions (FRAP method)**

259 The Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay determines the reduction of ferric ion
260 (Fe³⁺)-ligand complex to the intensely blue-coloured ferrous (Fe²⁺) complex. FRAP method
261 was performed by sequentially mixing 2,4,6-Tris(2-pyridyl)-s-triazine (10 mM in HCl (40
262 mM)), FeCl₃ (20 mM in H₂O) and CH₃CCONa buffer solution (0.3 M, pH = 3.6) with a ratio of

263 1:1:10 v/v/v, respectively. Each microemulsion (C = 6 mg/mL, 100 μ L) was added to a FRAP
264 solution (900 μ L) and stirred for 10 min. The absorbance of each sample was determined at
265 593 nm and results were expressed as Ascorbic Acid Equivalents (AAE). Experiments were
266 run in duplicate.

267

268 **2.2.4.5. High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy**

269 For a better insight, the morphology of nanoemulsions droplets were studied by
270 Transmission Electron Microscopy, especially to determine the location and distribution of
271 Lap particles. Analysed samples were prepared based on previously published
272 methodologies [45,46]. To do so, formulations were diluted (1:100) in distilled water and
273 placed on 300-mesh TEM copper grids (Neyco, Vanves, France). To provide samples with
274 high electron density, uranyl acetate (1% w/w, pH 4.0) was mixed with the diluted samples
275 and air-dried at room temperature, covered with a carbon film. Then, they were analysed
276 with high-resolution transmission electron microscope and HAADF FEI TITAN G2 (HRTEM).
277 The use of HRTEM was coupled with analytical electron microscopy performed with a
278 SUPER-X silicon-drift windowless energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) detector. The
279 AEM spectra were collected in STEM mode (Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy)
280 using a High Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) detector. Maps of the X-ray chemical
281 elements were also collected.

282

283 **2.2.4.6. Rheology**

284 The controlled rate viscometer RotoVisco 1 (Thermo Scientific HAAKE) was used for the
285 rheological characterization of Pickering emulsions (ECL_2L, EPS_2L, EAC_2L, EOQ_2L,
286 ECL_3L, EPS_3L, EAC_3L, EOQ_3L). The equipment was equipped with a plate/plate sensor
287 combination (\varnothing 20 mm serrated PP20S), set at a constant temperature of 25 $^{\circ}$ C (\pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C,
288 peltier temperature controller). Nanoemulsions without Lap particles were too liquid for
289 this sensor combination, so their rheological characterization was not possible. The flow
290 curves were obtained between 5-10 days after sample preparation. The selected shear rate
291 (70-800 1/s) reproduces the typical stresses for skin spreading (70 – 200 1/s), manual
292 mixing (100-200 1/s) and container filling and removal (400-2000 1/s) [47]. Six replicates
293 were obtained for each sample. Area Under the Curve (AUC, Pa/s) were calculated by
294 trapezoidal method of the upward and downward flow curves.

295

296 **2.2.4.7. In vitro Cytotoxicity**

297 Normal human dermal fibroblast cells (NHDFs from juvenile foreskin, PromoCell, WVR,
298 Italy) were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, Sigma-Aldrich, Italy)
299 supplemented with 200 IU/mL penicillin/0.2 mg/mL (Sigma-Aldrich, Italy) and 10% v/v fetal
300 bovine serum (FBS, Euroclone, Italy). NHDFs were seeded at a density of 35×10^3 cells/well
301 in 96-well plates and left to reach confluency. Nanoemulsions were diluted in full growth
302 medium prior cell contact for 24 h. Then, the MTT [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-
303 diphenyltetrazolium bromide] assay was carried out. The medium in each well was
304 removed and 100 μ L of MTT solution at 1 mg/mL in DMEM w/o phenol red (Sigma-Aldrich,
305 Milan, Italy) were added. Then, the cells substrates were incubated at 37 °C for 3 h, followed
306 by MTT solution removal and addition of 100 μ L of isopropanol (Carlo Erba, Italy). The
307 absorbance of each well was read using FLUOstar® Omega Microplate Reader (BMG
308 LABTECH, Italy) at $\lambda=570$ nm (with reference $\lambda = 690$ nm).

309 **2.2.5. Statistical Analysis**

310 Statistical analyses were performed using non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test for results
311 without normal distribution (p-value < 0.05), such as the *in vitro* cytotoxicity.

312 **3. Results and Discussion**

313 **3.1. Characterisation of Essential Oils**

314 **3.1.1. Analytical Characterization of Essential Oils**

315 The CEC-DAD methodology used for the analysis of EOs was optimised and fully validated
316 with nine terpenoid target compounds in terms of linearity, precision and accuracy. The
317 method sensitivity was 0.1 μ g/mL in terms of limit of quantitation (LOQ), while linearity was
318 good ($R^2 \geq 0.9990$) over the 0.1–200 μ g/mL range for all the analytes. Method precision was
319 also satisfactory, being the percentage relative standard deviation (RSD%) always < 5.4%,
320 while accuracy was $\geq 87\%$. Qualitative and quantitative results obtained from the analysis
321 of EO samples by applying this method are reported in **Table 3**.

322

323 Essential oil's composition is extremely heterogeneous and expected to quantitatively
324 change between samples due to differential growing conditions, nutrients, water, visible
325 light and ultraviolet radiation, plant age, among others [48–51]. Among the quantified
326 terpenoids, limonene is the main one detected in PS and OQ essential oils
327 [5,6,8,10,11,13,52–54]. In general, all the components detected, including minor ones,
328 agreed with the existing literature about their composition [6–8,13,14,55–57]. As far as

329 authors are concerned, it is the first time that the fruit EO from *B. graveolens* has been used
 330 and characterized, the wood and branches being the most studied source in this specie. β -
 331 caryophyllene was also expected to dominate in OQ, as previously reported [58,59].

332

333 The components reported in these EOs, including limonene, α -pinene, β -pinene and
 334 sabinene exert synergistic skin anti-aging effects by reducing the activity of hyaluronidase,
 335 elastase, collagenase, and amylase enzymes [60,61]. Components such as p-cymene and
 336 β -caryophyllene stand out by their antioxidant activity, which can also be used for
 337 maintaining a proper skin condition [62,63].

338 It is also worth to mention that other components are probably present in these EO, as
 339 reported in the literature [59,64], though they were not evaluated through the methodology
 340 employed in this manuscript.

341

342

Table 3. Analytical characterization of EOs. PS: B. graveolens; OQ: O. quixos.

Component (ng/mL)	PS	OQ
Limonene	1064.3	412.3
Sabinene	10.2	8.6
β -phellandrene	42.3	34.2
β -elemene	712.3	41.6
β -ocimene	523.2	16.3
β -pinene	22.3	139.4
α -pinene	36.3	254.6
β -caryophyllene	22.3	322.6
p-cymene	7.6	264.3

343

344 Elemene components have been explored and used as anticancer molecules[65,66],
 345 especially in China [67,68]. Although the anticancer effect is outside of the scope of the
 346 present study, PS EO could be a good candidate for anticancer therapy due to its β -elemene
 347 content.

348 On the other hand, β -caryophyllene (the second most common terpenoid quantified in OQ)
 349 proved useful in skin treatments such as atopic dermatitis [69], wound healing [70],
 350 epidermoid cancer [71] and melanoma [72,73]. Regarding skin cancer, limonene and
 351 sabinene have also proven effective [73], thus demonstrating the potential of both OQ and
 352 PS EO as active ingredient for skin disorders.

353 Other terpenes such as p-cymene (OQ EO) possesses a remarkable antimicrobial and
354 analgesic activity for skin conditions [74,75].

355

356 Moreover, terpenes in general are considered skin penetration enhancers [76], meaning
357 that the analysed EO (especially OQ due to β -caryophyllene) can be used as therapeutic
358 ingredients, and also as complementary or synergistic actives in other topical formulations
359 requiring effective absorption.

360 3.1.2. Antioxidant Activity of Essential Oils

361 The antioxidant activity of pristine EOs was measured by plotting the percentage of
362 inhibition of the free radical scavenging capacity of DPPH against the concentrations of
363 different standard solutions of EOs. As expected, each EO showed good antioxidant activity
364 that enhances with the increasing of EOs concentration. The free radical scavenging activity
365 expressed as IC₅₀, namely the concentration at which a 50% DPPH reduction is observed.
366 determined through DPPH assay for each EO is reported in **Table 4**.

367 Both EOs show comparable IC₅₀ values probably due to their chemical composition.
368 Compared to literature, the differences observed in IC₅₀ values are attributed to the
369 heterogeneous composition of the essential oil, variations in the extraction methods, the
370 plant part used, and its origin (**Table 4**). Moreover, the synergistic effects of chemical
371 components have also reported to exert a significant influence in the final antioxidant
372 activity [77].

373 *Table 4. Free radical scavenging activity (DPPH) of each essential oil expressed as IC₅₀ (mg/mL). Some DPPH*
374 *activity values from literature are also included as reference. IC₅₀ stands for "half-maximal inhibitory*
375 *concentration".*

EO	IC ₅₀ (mg/mL)	Literature values	
		IC ₅₀ (mg/mL)	Ref
PS (<i>B. graveolens</i>)	1.9 ± 0.9	22.9	[11]
		0.545	[7]
OQ (<i>O. quixos</i>)	1.9 ± 1.0	10.0	[58]
		2.79	[15]

376 Limonene, β -elemene and β -ocimene predominated in PS. Although limonene was also the
377 main component of the PS reported by Fon-Fay and co-workers [11], their essential oil had
378 a free radical scavenging activity of 23 mg/mL (IC₅₀). In other cases, limonene was found in
379 low amounts in a PS essential oil [7] that showed remarkably higher DPPH activity (**Table**
380 **4**). The free-radical scavenging activity of OQ (extracted from leaves) was one of the highest
381 ones found in the literature [15,58].

382 These observations confirm the fact that synergistic activities between components are
383 crucial for antioxidant properties. In any case, antagonist effects have also been found,
384 especially for non-oxygenated and oxygenated monoterpenes [77], which could explain the
385 differential antioxidant activities in different EOs.

386 **3.2. Nanoemulsions characterization**

387 **3.2.1. Qualitative, macroscopic analysis: physical behaviour**

388 Emulsions are thermodynamically unstable systems, undergoing instability phenomena
389 such as creaming (or sedimentation), flocculation, coalescence of phase separation. The
390 accelerated stability tests were performed at 8, 25 and 40°C, results gathered in **Table 5**
391 and **Figure S2**.

392 All the samples tested reported remarkable syneresis or phase separation when subjected
393 at 40°C, even 24 h after their preparation. According to the observations (**Table 5**) EPS_2L
394 and EOQ_2L were the most stable formulations, not showing remarkable signs of instability
395 with respect to their counterparts (EPS and EOQ). In general terms, PS formulations
396 showed the highest stability, since EOQ_3L started to show syneresis after 7 days at room
397 temperature (25°C), which did not happen for EPS_3L until day 14th.

398

399 Clay minerals are known by their ability to increase stability of suspensions and emulsions
400 due to their ability to form a house-of-cards based internal network in aqueous (unmodified
401 clays) or non-aqueous environments (organomodified clays of organoclays) [78]. This
402 statement is somehow contradictory with some of the results herein reported.

403 The thorough study developed by Nciri et al. revealed that the addition of smectites to an
404 olive oil-in-water emulsion could either jeopardize or improve emulsion stability [29]. On
405 one hand, at low surfactant concentration clay particles decreased emulsion stability due
406 to i) competition between the clay particles and surfactant molecules for the interface. In
407 this case, the clay particle would act as “surfactant”, though with lower efficacy, thus
408 explaining lower stabilities. Alternatively, ii) surfactant molecules could adsorb to clay
409 surface or interlayer space rather than on the oil-in-water interface [25,29]. Nciri and co-
410 workers also reported that increases in surfactant concentration could compensate for
411 clay particles effects, thus improving the overall stability of the emulsion. For the present
412 study, fixed concentrations of surfactant, water and oil phases were employed. The
413 heterogeneous and complex composition of both EOs (**Table 3**) could influence the
414 stability, since different HLBs will be required according to the polarity of the components.
415 In the absence of Lap, all emulsions were stable for 28 days, since no competition between

416 clay particles and surfactant happened. For their counterparts with Lap, the influence of
 417 mineral particles with surfactant, together with the potential difference in HLB for each EO
 418 justifies the necessity of a case-by-case optimization of surfactant-clay concentrations.
 419 These hypotheses are also supported by a similar study evaluating Lap as emulsion
 420 stabilizer [25] and other Pickering emulsions [33].

421

422 Regarding the higher instability of nanoemulsions with 3% w/w Lap, it is easy to imagine
 423 that as higher the particle concentration, the higher the emulsion stability due to the
 424 formation of a continuous Lap network (Lap gel) preventing droplets coalescence.
 425 Nevertheless, some Pickering emulsion studies have revealed that “high concentration of
 426 particles does not always result in a dense coverage (...) of the droplets” and thus, higher
 427 stability [33]. In fact, low particles concentrations have proven to successfully stabilise
 428 nanoemulsion. The stability results obtained are also aligned with previous studies on
 429 essential oils, where laponite was proposed as Pickering emulsifier together with kaolinite
 430 and sepiolite [79]. These authors reported that Lap concentrations higher than 1% w/w
 431 apparently resulted counter-productive for formulation stability.

432 Additionally, it is well known that EOs effectively interact with smectite clays (natural
 433 analogous of Lap) by integrating in the clay interlayer space, which ultimately improves the
 434 stability of EO [80–82]. Under these circumstances, another hypothesis can be proposed:
 435 the interaction between Lap and EO components in the emulsion could trigger instabilities
 436 by means of component’s imbalance. In other words, the interactions between EO
 437 molecules and clays could “withdraw” oil phase, thus unbalancing the emulsion system.

438

439 *Table 5. Macroscopic, qualitative results of accelerated stability test. Symbols: (✓) indicates no signs of*
 440 *macroscopic instability; (x) for samples showing macroscopic instability; (*) indicates moderate syneresis; (**)*
 441 *remarkable syneresis; (***) moderate creaming.*

Qualitative stability

Time (days)	1			7			14			28		
	8	25	40	8	25	40	8	25	40	8	25	40
EPS	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
EOQ	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
EPS_2L	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
EOQ_2L	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
EPS_3L	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x	*	*	x	*	x	x
EOQ_3L	✓	✓	x	✓	*	x	*	*	x	x	x	x
✓	No signs of macroscopic instability detected											

(*), (**), (***)	Instability: syneresis (*, **) or creaming (***)
x	Clear instability: remarkable syneresis and/or phase separation

442

443 Simultaneously, macroscopic changes in consistency were also monitored at room
 444 temperature (**Fig. 1** and **Fig. S2**). While EPS and EOQ emulsions maintained their liquid
 445 consistency throughout the experiment, emulsions with Lap increased their texture either
 446 from liquid to viscous (for EPS_2L and EOQ_2L) or from viscous to creamy (for EPS_3L,
 447 EOQ_3L), due to the ability of Lap to swell, assuming the appearance of strong inorganic
 448 gels at short times. It is well known that Lap aqueous suspensions (as any other layered
 449 clay) take some time to swell, thus improving the final viscosity [83]. These consistency
 450 changes were desirable to improve the skin spreadability of the prepared emulsions, since
 451 excessive fluidity could hinder their permanence over the skin.

452 **3.2.2. DLS droplet size, polydispersity index and ζ -potential studies**

453 The size of emulsion droplets are measured by DLS (**Fig. 2**). The low viscosity and interfacial
 454 tension of essential oils enable them to produce emulsions with small droplet sizes.
 455 Pristine EPS and EOQ emulsions presented a stable size (67-183 nm) and PDI for 28 days.
 456 According to this droplet size range, micro-and nano-emulsion nomenclature can be use
 457 [20–23] d. During the first 14 days, all the emulsions reported a hydrodynamic EO droplet
 458 size < 300 nm (67-299 nm), even after the addition of Lap. EOQ reported the smallest
 459 droplet size, which are somehow related to the OQ essential oil composition and/or polarity
 460 (**Table 3**) since it reported significant differences in quantitative composition. This affects
 461 the equilibrium of the OQ emulsion, making the required HLB more optimal with the same
 462 amount of surfactant and, therefore, resulting in smaller droplet sizes.

463 In all cases the addition of Lap induced an increase in average droplet size, more
 464 pronounced with increasing Lap concentration (2% w/w emulsions vs. 3% w/w), **Fig. 2,**
 465 **right**. The larger particle increase of emulsions with clay particles are related to either Lap
 466 aggregates in the aqueous phase or to the formation of Lap Pickering emulsions [84]
 467 (accumulation of Lap particles in the interphase). As a result, a bigger and wider droplet
 468 size range is obtained, which is more consistent with "nanoemulsion" nomenclature [20–
 469 23].

470

471 Lap nanoemulsions showed a droplet size increase after 28 days for both essential oils,
 472 accompanied by an increase in PDI values. This is consistent with the qualitative results
 473 reported in **Table 5**. Increases in nanoemulsion droplet size through time have already been

474 reported after the addition of clays and other particles for Pickering
475 emulsification[33,85,86]. Nciri et al. ascribed the increase in nanoemulsion droplet size to
476 the adsorption of surfactant molecules on clay particles [29], meaning that the results
477 herein reported, are expectable. As an alternative hypothesis, the increase in droplet size
478 can also be ascribed to the preparation method [85], since Lap was added to an already
479 prepared emulsion under mild conditions (magnetic stirring). The presence of clay particles
480 could destabilize the system and so, modify the final droplet's size.

481

482 Following the indications of the ISO 22412:2017 on DLS particle size analysis,
483 monodisperse samples are those defined by a Pdl < 0.05, while Pdl > 0.7 corresponds to
484 highly polydisperse samples. At short times (0 – 14 days) all the nanoemulsions reported a
485 Pdl between 0.2-0.6 (**Fig. 2, left**). Highly polydispersity (Pdl > 0.7) was found for EPS_3L and
486 EOQ_3L after 28 days (**Fig. 2, left**), in alignment with the stability studies already reported
487 (**Table 5**).

488

489 Limonene-based emulsions with clear appearance have reported smaller Pdl and better
490 time-stability[87]. These observations agree with the results of EPS and EPS_2L, showing a
491 clearer appearance (**Fig. S2**), better time-stability (**Table 5**) and stable DLS and Pdl values
492 (**Fig. 2**). A similar trend was observed for EOQ and EOQ_2L, although they were more turbid
493 in appearance.

494 The addition of 3% w/w of Lap introduced some changes in the physicochemical properties
495 of the formulation. This result is ascribed to different modes of contact between the
496 emulsion droplets and particles in the so-called “Pickering emulsions”, thus modifying the
497 droplets size [28]. On the contrary, 2% w/w Lap did not influence the stability in a significant
498 manner with respect to EOQ and EPS, indicating a higher equilibrium between the emulsion
499 components for 28 days.

500

501 Zeta potential (ZP) measurements are gathered in **Fig. 3B**. High absolute ZP induces
502 emulsion stability due to repulsion phenomena, thus minimizing flocculation and
503 coalescence [40,88]. ZP is affected by changes at the interface with the continuous phase,
504 caused by dissociation of surface molecules from particles [89]. The addition of 2% and 3%
505 of Lap (**Fig. 3**) enabled a more negative net charge of the whole system, which could
506 improve system stability if particles are adequately distributed, and the system is in
507 equilibrium [46]. Contradictorily, EPS_2L and EOQ_2L had, in general, more negative ZP
508 than their counterparts EPS_3L and EOQ_3L even if the amount of Lap was higher. In other

509 words, an excess of Lap concentration is counterproductive for ZP values. The droplets
510 coalescence indicated by DLS and Pdl (**Fig. 2**) for EPS_3L and EOQ_3L can be related to ZP.

511 **3.2.3 pH assessment**

512 The pH assessment was conducted as an additional strategy to assess the stability of
513 emulsions during the storage period (**Fig. 3B**). A change in pH may represent degradation of
514 the EOs, bacterial proliferation, instability, or incompatibility of some components, being
515 that the pH influences widely the electrical charge of the groups of the components of the
516 systems. Moreover, the pH is of special importance for cutaneous administration. The pH
517 value of nanoemulsions without LAP varied from 4.8 to 5 in all cases, compatible with the
518 natural acidic pH of the skin. Different emulsions with essential oils reported similar pH
519 values [89–91].

520 The addition of LAP increased the pH around 9-10 (**Fig. 3**), as it is expected for clay minerals
521 suspensions and already studied Pickering emulsions [32,92]. Despite some of the
522 instabilities reported in some formulations, the pH values of all the emulsions remained
523 unchanged for 28 days, indicating the absence of chemical degradations or ulterior
524 incompatibilities. Microbiological growth was also discarded in view of the pH stability,
525 although specific studies should be performed to confirm this fact.

526 Other implications of pH results are worth discussing. The resultant pH after LAP addition
527 is far from the optimal natural skin pH (approximately 5 – 5.5), which can be detrimental
528 form some patients. Nevertheless, clay minerals act as pH buffers, making pH control a
529 difficult task in their presence. Additionally, clay particles usually exert their maximum
530 potential as rheology ingredients at their natural pH: any modification of the final pH of the
531 clay suspension could result in inadequate viscosity [93,94]. *In view of all this, no studies
532 about pH adjustment are included in this manuscript, since this step would require a
533 thorough study and strict selection and monitoring of additional variables, which were
534 considered outside the scope of the present study. Further studies are needed to evaluate
535 and correct the topical safety of the formulation pH.*

536 **3.2.4. Antioxidant Activity of Nanoemulsions**

537 Since the methanol, present as solvent, in DPPH method led to the disruption of
538 nanoemulsions, it cannot be applied to study their free radical scavenger's activity. The
539 antioxidant activity of EPS and EOQ was evaluated by FRAP method. The obtained results
540 were expressed as equivalents of ascorbic acid (AAE), used as standard (**Table 6**).

541 In this case, both EPS and EOQ formulations showed very similar reducing power, as it
 542 happened for the DPPH activity of their corresponding EOs before formulation. In other
 543 words, by comparing the relative reducing power activity of emulsions with the relative free
 544 radical scavenging, it seems clear that the oil-in-water systems are not changing
 545 significantly the antioxidant performance of both actives.

546 *Table 6. Reducing power of EO emulsions by FRAP method. Results are expressed as Ascorbic Acid Equivalents*
 547 *(AAE, $\mu\text{mol/L}$).*

Nanoemulsion	AAE ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)
EPS	31.6 \pm 0.07
EOQ	32.7 \pm 0.07

548

549 **3.2.5. High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy**

550 EPS nanoemulsions were chosen as representatives for microscopic analysis due to their
 551 time stability. Typical appearance of EPS nanoemulsion was confirmed (**Fig. 4A** and **4B**).
 552 The XEDS analysis of this sample revealed the absence of inorganic matter, only formed by
 553 N, O and C.

554 **Fig. 4B, 4C** and **4D** include particle size distribution of droplet determined by
 555 measurements through ImageJ software. Compared with the DLS measurements, the HR-
 556 TEM results showed slightly higher sizes. Differential sizes can be explained by differential
 557 techniques, as well as by the fact that HR-TEM samples were dried. In any case, the size
 558 trend of EPS samples was also confirmed by microscopy, since EPS_2L and EPS_3L
 559 samples showed higher droplet diameters with respect to the formulation without Lap.

560

561 The role of Lap as stabilizer can be confirmed by the double-layered droplets in EPS_2L and
 562 EPS_3L, a feature previously reported for Pickering emulsions [26]. This can be explained
 563 by the arrangement of Lap particles in the nanoemulsion liquid-liquid interface, together
 564 with polysorbate 80, thus forming the so-called Pickering emulsion. This “shell” around oil
 565 droplets increased in thickness in EPS_3L with respect to EPS_2L, indicating the formation
 566 of multiple layers of Lap particles (and or polysorbate 80) at the oil/water interface [28],
 567 which could explain the increase of droplet size reported by DLS to a certain degree. The
 568 accumulation of Lap particles around EO droplets was further confirmed by the spectra in

569 **Fig. 4E**, showing that the amount of Si and Mg is higher at the droplet edge. This fact can
570 also be visible in the mapped images (**Fig. 4E to 4L**), forming a sharper ring. The study of
571 Zheng et al. [27] proposed the formation of a Lap sheet around oil droplets, followed by
572 surfactant micelles as external sheets. In the present case, the mapping analysis shows an
573 apparent accumulation of Si (from Lap) both in the internal and external sheet of the oil-in-
574 water interfacial space, indicating that Lap particles may be combined with the surfactant
575 at all levels of the so-called oil droplet “shell”.

576 More particularly, the clearest parts in **Fig. 4I** (HAADF) show higher intensity in Si and Mg
577 maps (**Fig. 4K and 4L**), indicating the accumulation of Lap particles [95]. This fact has
578 already been reported for Pickering emulsions with high particle concentrations [33,95],
579 where densely-packed particle areas coexisted with areas weakly covered. Authors like
580 Vignati et al. [31] stated that low particle concentration around emulsion droplets were
581 more prone to redistribute in the interface and so, prevent droplet coalescence.

582 Minor quantities of silicon and magnesium of the Lap can also be found inside the particles
583 as well as outside them, so the formation of a network of Lap particles in the continuous
584 phase (as proposed by Velandia et al. [28]) cannot be dismissed

585

586 **3.2.6. Rheology**

587 In general, the prepared emulsions showed low shear stress values, below 30 Pa in all
588 cases (**Fig. 5A**). Despite the fluctuations (probably caused by their low viscosity), all of them
589 showed a pseudoplastic-like profile. Regarding the time-dependent properties, ECL_2L
590 and EPS_2L showed a rheopectic flow curve, since their downward curves (dashed lines)
591 showed higher shear stress values (**Fig. 5A**). This behaviour, although possible (especially
592 for clay suspensions [96–98]), is less common for Pickering emulsions [99–101]. The rest of
593 the samples showed a thixotropic curve, which can be induced by the “break up” of particle
594 agglomerates under shear stress and reform along with the reduction of the stress applied
595 (**Fig. 5A**). The AUC (Area Under the Curve, **Fig. 5B**) represents the total energy dissipation or
596 the energy required for a material to be deformed, given a shear rate range. It also quantifies
597 the thixotropic and rheopectic characteristics of the samples. In this case, the AUC (Pa/s)
598 indicated that EOQ_3L and EPS_3L needed similar amount of energy to flow (**Fig. 5B**). In
599 these cases, the AUCs showed a positive value, typical of thixotropic samples. EOQ_2L and
600 EPS_2L also reported (in absolute terms) similar dissipation energies, which agree with the
601 Lap concentration of both pairs of samples. While EOQ_2L exhibited a positive AUC,
602 suggesting thixotropic behavior, EPS_2L showed a negative AUC, characteristic of

603 rheopexy. Rheopexy is related with the “reorganization” or “formation” of the internal
604 network structure of the sample during stress application. These results confirm that
605 increasing amounts of Lap are beneficial for topical application, since increases the time-
606 dependency as well as the absolute AUC value. It is also worth mentioning the size of the
607 standard error for each AUC, indicating that some of the hysteresis loops are just apparent.
608 Similar fluctuations have also been observed by Chen et al. [101] and ascribed to
609 inhomogeneity of preparations or pre-shear effect during sample handling. The former
610 alternative could make sense since Lap was added by magnetic stirring. Moreover,
611 inhomogeneities could also be ascribed to sample’s instability (section 3.2.1).

612 As widely known rheological additive, Lap addition increased formulations consistency and
613 so, their shear stress and viscosity values [99]. The presence of multilayered Lap particles
614 in the continuous phase (as proved by HRTEM studies) is agrees with the higher consistency
615 of 3% w/w Lap emulsions. For EPS nanoemulsions, a 1% w/w increase in Lap even induced
616 an inversion in the hysteresis loop (EPS_2L vs EPS_3L, **Fig. 5A and 5B**).

617 The nature and composition of the EO is a determinant factor for the resultant rheological
618 properties. This can be related to the required HLB of each nanoemulsion (determined by
619 the oil phase) and the different interactions between Lap-surfactant in the interface [28].
620 Samples with PS essential oil showed higher viscosity values with respect to OQ (**Fig. 5C,**
621 **5D**). As stated by Bains and Pal [86], “the dispersions (emulsions or suspensions) become
622 more viscous upon decreasing the size of the inclusions”. Therefore, considering the DLS
623 results (**Fig. 2**), EOQ_2L should have presented higher viscosities than EPS_2L, specially at
624 short times. The hydrogen-bonding ability of the liquid medium (the EO) with the stabilizing
625 particles has also been proposed as an explanation for differential rheological behaviour in
626 Pickering emulsions [99,100]. Therefore, we hypothesize that the rheology differences
627 between these samples (specially between EPS_2L and EOQ_2L) may be related to the
628 differential interaction of the Lap at the EOQ and EPS interfaces and continuous phase,
629 determined by the compositional differences of EOs.

630 The viscosity (**Fig. 5C and 5D**) has also been considered as a feature to differentiate micro-
631 and nanoemulsions, the latter one usually having around ≤ 1 cP (0.001 Pa·s) at room
632 temperature [20,102], with no defined value for microemulsion. According to this criterion,
633 EPS_2L, EPS_3L, EOQ_2L and EOQ_3L can be considered “microemulsions” since they
634 showed 4000-10 cP dynamic viscosity (4-0.01 Pa·s). That was the point in adding Lap, to
635 increase the final viscosity of the original system. In fact, EPS and EOQ flow curves could

636 not be obtained with the existing equipment, which leads us to think that EPS and EOQ
637 viscosity was closer to 0.001 Pa·s viscosity, a closer behaviour to “nanoemulsions”.

638 **3.2.7. *In vitro* Cytotoxicity**

639 The cytotoxicity results against human fibroblasts (NHDFs) are gathered in **Fig. 6**. The non-
640 parametric statistical analysis of Mann-Whitney revealed significant differences between
641 the cell viability among studied samples. Any free EO (neither at 1:400 or 1:800) impaired
642 cell viability. This could be related to the low solubility of EO in the culture medium. No
643 significant differences were found between the control (GM) and free EO despite the
644 apparent proliferative effect showed by free EO (**Fig. 6C**). EPS showed slightly smaller cell
645 viability than free PS, but higher than formulations containing 2% Lap. This trend can be
646 observed for both 1:400 and 1:800 formulations, though these differences were not found
647 statistically significant for this EO.

648 Essential oils have been proposed as cytotoxic agents for cancer cells [103,104]. Although
649 the mechanism is still to be defines, it seems clear that EO components must permeate
650 cell membranes to exert this effect. The results herein reported suggest that free EO cannot
651 interact with cells, reporting no effect over their viability.

652

653 Contrary to EPS, EOQ emulsion (without Lap) showed statistically significant reduction in
654 cell viability (**Fig. 6C**), improving after Lap addition (EOQ_2L and EOQ_3L). This viability
655 reduction was not detected in 1:800 studies (**Fig. 6D**).

656 The reduction of cell viability caused by emulsions (concentration-dependent) in
657 comparison with free EO have been majorly related to polysorbate 80. Nevertheless,
658 possible toxicity of EO components, whose cellular uptake, interactions and/or possible
659 endocytosis, cannot be dismissed. In any case, the surfactant plays a crucial role
660 (endocytosis can be mediated by direct interaction via the surfactant, through electrostatic
661 attraction) [105]. Previous works reported that certain surfactants are detrimental for cell
662 viability [106–109], something expectable since these compounds can damage cell
663 membrane to a different extent depending on their origin and concentration. In fact, some
664 of them (i.e. TritonX-100) are commonly used to increase cell permeability during cellular
665 staining. The cytotoxicity of polysorbates is concentration-dependent [108] and related to
666 their HLB value [109]. According to some studies, this cytotoxicity is associated to the
667 induction of cell oxidative stress [110–113].

668 If the differential results of cell viability between EOQ and EPS are ascribable to polysorbate
669 80, they could indicate that EOQ possessed higher surfactant concentration, thus leading

670 to “free polysorbate”, more prone to interact with cell membranes. Under these conditions,
671 this emulsion should show greater stability, something confirmed by some previous results
672 such as ζ -potential (stable for 28 days, **Fig. 3**). Likewise, EOQ reported the slightest
673 differences in DLS dimensions (**Fig. 2**) for 28 days (67.32 to 78.21 nm) in comparison with
674 EPS (from 183 to 148 nm). In other words, the polysorbate 80 concentration used for EOQ
675 was optimal for emulsion stability but can hinder *in vitro* cytocompatibility.

676

677 As previously mentioned, the increase in cytotoxicity for EPS and EOQ formulations can
678 also be attributed to droplet permeability. Wooster et al. [105] worked with caco-2 cells and
679 observed that O/W emulsions improved the bioavailability of hydrophobic oil components
680 by facilitating their interaction with cell membranes. In other words, an increased cellular
681 uptake—potentially via endocytosis and aided by surfactants like polysorbate—lead to
682 greater cytotoxicity compared to bulk EO, which is poorly absorbed and largely
683 inaccessible to cells.

684

685 The addition of 2% Lap significantly reduced *in vitro* cell viability at 1:400 dilution in EPS_2L
686 (**Fig. 6A**), influence that disappeared at higher dilutions (**Fig. 6B**). EPS_3L did not show
687 significant differences with respect to EPS nor Free PS (**Fig. 6A**), highlighting a positive
688 effect of Lap. In fact, 3% w/w Lap Pickering emulsions did not show statistically significant
689 differences with respect to control (GM) in any of the samples, except for EOQ_3L at dilution
690 1:800 (reporting slight cell proliferation, **Fig. 6D**). EPS_3L 1:800 also showed a cell viability
691 slightly higher than 100%, though not statistically significant. The biocompatibility of Lap
692 has been confirmed by multiple studies, as reviewed by Kiaee et al. [114], both *in vitro* and
693 *in vivo*. In fact, the ability of Lap to reduce the cytotoxicity of certain drugs have also been
694 reported [115] which is in agreement with our results.

695

696 The complex interactions between EOs, polysorbate 80 and Lap highly determine the final
697 properties of the formulations. The differences between 2% and 3% w/w Lap formulations
698 are difficult to explain, since no similar studies have been found in the literature that
699 include cytotoxicity studies (as far as authors are concerned). The study of Imbriano et al.
700 stated that the addition of clay minerals in nanoemulsions reported cell viability reduction
701 [117], in accordance with the viability results of EPS_2L and EOQ_2L (1:400, **Fig. 6A** and
702 **6C**). This observation has been ascribed to the possible precipitation of clay particles over
703 the cell monolayer [118,119], thus impairing nutrients and oxygen flow. If this were the main
704 cause of viability reduction for EPS_2L and EOQ_2L, the corresponding formulations with

705 3% Lap would present smaller viabilities, which is not the case. On the contrary, other
706 articles reported that Pickering emulsions are expected to improve cell viability due to the
707 absence/reduction of surfactants [120], this statement in agreement with 3% w/w Lap
708 formulations. Proliferative trends have been observed for clay suspensions in previous
709 studies, probably associated with the release of some cations and other elements
710 [118,121].

711

712 The interactions between clay particles and surfactants are widely known [29,34,122],
713 something previously mentioned in section 3.2.1 as a possible explanation for stability
714 results. Bearing in mind all the previous results, it can be hypothesized that:

715 - In Lap-polysorbate 80 Pickering emulsions, clay particles and surfactant establish
716 some sort of interactions that lead to the formation of a dense interface (**Fig. 4**)
717 around EO droplets [27,28]. So, the EO is surrounded by a multilayer, compact
718 “shell” of Lap and polysorbate 80 micelles, electrostatically attracted. The
719 aqueous, continuous phase is formed by Lap network (typical house-of-cards) and
720 polysorbate micelles detached from the droplet shell.

721 - In emulsions with 2% Lap (EPS_2L and EOQ_2L), the continuous phase formed by
722 Lap particles was not viscous enough (see rheology curves, **Fig. 5**). This lower
723 viscosity enables polysorbate micelles to move more freely, not having enough Lap
724 particles to interact with. Therefore, they were more prone to reach cell
725 membranes.

726 - In emulsions with 3% Lap (EPS_3L and EOQ_3L), a higher amount of Lap particles
727 can be found in the continuous phase, providing higher viscosities and hysteresis
728 loops. Due to that fact, more interactions occur between Lap and Polysorbate 80,
729 which could explain increase in droplet size (**Fig. 2**) and lower stability showed by
730 these samples (**Table 5**). In other words, Lap particles “steal” polysorbate
731 molecules from the oil-water interface. Nevertheless, these interactions and the
732 viscous Lap network in the continuous phase prevents/slows down surfactant
733 micelles and EO O/W droplets to reach cell membranes, thus explaining the cell
734 viability results.

735 4. Free EO was found non cytotoxic due to its low ability to permeate cells,
736 contrary to EOQ and EPS. In the latter case, the small droplet sizes and the
737 presence of surfactant, can promote EO cell absorption and thus,
738 cytotoxicity. The presence of Lap is a good alternative to modulate this toxic
739 effect (due to either the EO, the surfactant, or both). Apart from the above-
740 mentioned effects interactions with polysorbate molecules, this
741 “modulation” by Lap also implies bigger droplets, which could hinder the
742 skin permeation of encapsulated EOs. Nevertheless, clays can ensure
743 sustained contact of the emulsion with the skin, supporting gradual and
744 enhanced permeation [116]. **Conclusions**

745 The essential oils of *Bursera graveolens* (PS) and *Ocotea quixos* (OQ) Amazon rainforest
746 species, widely known by their therapeutic activities (from antioxidant to insect repellent
747 activity) were formulated as nanoemulsions and Pickering emulsions. The characteristics,
748 stability and properties of the resultant formulations were studied and compared.

749 The antioxidant activity of free and emulsified essential oils was quantified through DPPH
750 and FRAP methods, respectively. Their formulation as oil-in-water nanoemulsions, though
751 stable for 28 days, presented limited rheology properties (such as viscosity), hindering their
752 use as topical formulations. To solve this problem, laponite was proposed as additional
753 stabilizer. At a macroscopic level 3% w/w Lap induced faster instability, probably due to its
754 interactions with the surfactant (polysorbate 80). Lap caused an increment in droplet size,
755 negative net charge and sub-optimal pH. Further studies and additional excipients are
756 needed to adjust these parameters. Microscopy analysis (HR-TEM) of one sample
757 confirmed the formation of Pickering emulsions, where Lap particles and polysorbate 80
758 micelles combine in a multi-layered interface around oil droplets. Free essential oils were
759 biocompatible towards normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF), while nanoemulsions
760 (without Lap) exerted different degrees of cytotoxicity, associated to polysorbate 80 and/or
761 the cellular permeation of EO droplets. The toxic effects can be modulated and reduced by
762 Lap particles. That is, the presence of high amounts of laponite, although not optimal for
763 formulation stability, is useful for rheological and biocompatibility reasons. That is, 3% w/w
764 laponite formulations reported faster emulsion destabilization and higher droplet size.
765 Nevertheless, these same formulations reported higher viscosities, thixotropy and shear-
766 thinning profiles (enhancing skin spreadability) as well as full biocompatibility towards
767 NHDFs. The higher biocompatibility of formulations could also suggest lower cell

768 permeation ability of emulsion droplets. The implications of droplet size modification for
769 skin permeation require further investigation.

770

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779

780 **Declaration of Interest**

781 None.

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Supplementary Information

Figure S1. DPPH inhibition curve (%) for PS (A) and OQ (B).

Figure S2. Vials containing emulsions prepared after 1 day (left) and 28 days (right) under different temperatures (8, 25 and 40 °C).